

Short name	CCS Directive	Long name	Implementation of the EU CCS Directive
Geographic scope	EU Member States		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>The EU CCS Directive provides a comprehensive regulatory framework for CCS that EU member states must transpose into national law.</p> <p>The Directive contains provisions for the whole value chain, i.e., capture, transport and storage. It covers storage site selection and exploration permits, storage permits, operation closure and post-closure obligations, third party access, as well as general provisions etc.</p> <p>All Member States have the Directive. How MS have chosen to transpose the directive into national law has varied in terms of e.g. amendment of existing legislation v. implementation of new legislative framework, permitting storage, and length of post-close monitoring periods prior to transfer of liability. Also, there is a varying degree of maturity and details in the national frameworks, with respect to e.g. permitting regime and regulatory oversight. The degree of implementation will be studied and included in WP3.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>Some of the regulators may not be ready to issue permits at this stage, irrespective of positive results related to geologic mapping. Lack of maturity and details in the implemented framework may further represent legal uncertainty and confusion for market participants, which in turn may deter new projects. Also, variation in the implementation of CCS related legislation can create uncertainty regarding the long-term liability of project participants.</p> <p>This can cause problems with enforcement of rules foreseen by the CCS Directive, including the consistent monitoring of storage sites.</p> <p>Any inconsistencies between national legislation can cause challenges to the cross-border collaboration between two countries to store CO₂ as all details have then to be clarified in advance.</p>		
Other issues this affects	Investment certainty (economic issue), permitting process, liability		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directive 2009/31/EC; Official Journal of the European Union; https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32009L0031 • Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide (COM(2014) 99 final, Brussels, 25.2.2014) (First Implementation Report); https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52014DC0099&from=EN • Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide (COM(2017) 37 final, Brussels, 		

	<p>1.2.2017 (Second Implementation Report); https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0037&from=EN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide (COM(2019) 566 final, Brussels, 31.10.2019 (Third Implementation Report); https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0566&from=EN• Shogenova, A., et al. (2014). Implementation of the EU CCS Directive in Europe: results and development in 2013. Energy Procedia, 63, 6662-6670. https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1876610214009533• CO2GeoNet. (2021). State-of-play on CO2 geological storage in 32 European countries — an update. https://www.co2geonet.com/en/capacity-building/library-of-publications/technical-reports-and-scientific-publications/state-of-play-on-co2-geological-storage-in-32-european-countries-an-update/
--	---